

Table S1. Data origins for the 14 different states included in our dataset.

State	Data/Years	Source(s)
Alabama	PPH: 2011-2022 Harvest: 2013-2024 Number of hunters: 2013-2024	Alabama Department of Conservation and Natural Resources. (2025). Eastern Wild Turkey Research. < https://www.outdooralabama.com/research/eastern-wild-turkey-research > Accessed August 2025. 2014-2020 Full Fans and Sharp Spurs Reports Duda, M. D., M. Jones, T. Beppler, A. Center, A. Criscione, P. Doherty, G. L. Hughes, J. Morris, and A. Lanier. (2024). Alabama hunter harvest 2023-2024. Responsive Management National Office, Harrisonburg, Virginia, USA. Duda, M. D., M. Jones, T. Beppler, S. J. Bissell, A. Center, A. Criscione, P. Doherty, G. L. Hughes, C. Gerken, and A. Lanier. (2020). Alabama hunter harvest 2019-2020. Responsive Management National Office, Harrisonburg, Virginia, USA. Bryant, S. (2018). Alabama hunting survey 2016-2017. Grant Number W-35, Study 6. Alabama Division of Wildlife and Freshwater Fisheries: Wildlife Restoration Program, Montgomery, AL, USA.
Arkansas	PPH: 2010-2023 Harvest: 2012-2025 Number of hunters: 2021-2025	Arkansas Game and Fish Commission. (2025). Turkey Harvest and Scientific Reports. < https://www.agfc.com/education/turkey-harvest-and-scientific-reports/ > Accessed August 2025. 2010-2018 Arkansas Wild Turkey Brood Survey Summaries 2012-2018 Arkansas Statewide Turkey Harvest Report 2019-2024 Arkansas Turkey Program Annual Reports Estimated number of turkey hunters for 2021-2025 provided by David Moscicki, Turkey Program Coordinator, Arkansas Game and Fish Commission

Florida	PPH: 2019-2022 Harvest: 2021-2024 Number of hunters: 2021-2024	Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission. (2025). Wild turkey summer survey. < https://myfwc.com/hunting/turkey/brood-survey/ > Accessed October 2025. Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission. (2025). Wild Turkey Management Program. < https://myfwc.com/hunting/turkey/ > Accessed October 2025. 2021-2024 Annual Wild Turkey Hunting Status Report
Georgia	PPH: 2015-2022 Harvest: 2017-2024 Number of hunters: 2017-2024 (No estimate of harvest/hunters available for 2023)	Georgia Department of Natural Resources – Wildlife Resources Division. (2025). Brood survey dashboard. < https://www.arcgis.com/apps/dashboards/1741090889204f58ba17113fce755717 > Accessed August 2025. Georgia Department of Natural Resources – Wildlife Resources Division. (2025). Wild Turkey Program FY2024 Harvest Monitoring. Georgia Department of Natural Resources – Wildlife Resources Division, Social Circle, Georgia, USA.
Indiana	PPH: 2000-2022 Harvest: 2002-2024 Number of hunters: 2002-2020	Byers, A.M., & McCallen, E.B. (2024). Wild turkey summer brood production indices – 2024. Indiana Department of Natural Resources – Division of Fish and Wildlife, Indianapolis, Indiana, USA. Indiana Department of Natural Resources – Division of Fish and Wildlife. (2025). Wild Turkey Spring Harvest Data. < https://www.in.gov/dnr/fish-and-wildlife/hunting-and-trapping/wild-turkey-hunting-biology-and-management/wild-turkey-spring-harvest-data/ > Accessed October 2025. Backs, S. E. (2020). Spring wild turkey harvest results – 2020. Publication No. 2064. Indiana Department of Natural Resources – Division of Fish and Wildlife, Indianapolis, Indiana, USA.
Iowa	PPH: 2008-2023 Harvest: 2010-2025	Coffey, J.M. (2024). 2023-2024 Wild Turkeys. Iowa Department of Natural Resources, Des Moines, IA USA.

Iowa Department of Natural Resources. (2025). Deer & Turkey Harvest Report.
<<https://gooutdoorsiowa.com/RealTimeHarvestReport.aspx>> Accessed October 2025.

Kentucky
PPH: 2019-2022
Harvest: 2021-2024

Kentucky Department of Fish & Wildlife Resources. (2025). Summer turkey brood survey.
<<https://fw.ky.gov/Hunt/Pages/TurkeyBroodSurvey.aspx>> Accessed August 2025.

Kentucky Department of Fish & Wildlife Resources. (2025). Harvest Report Explorer.
<<https://app.fw.ky.gov/harvestdata/Records/Records?animal=Turkey&report=resultsTotal>>
Accessed October 2025.

Mississippi
PPH: 2014-2022
Harvest: 2016-2024
Number of hunters:
2021-2024

Butler, A.B, K.D., Godwin, S., Polles, and R., Cook. (2017). Mississippi's comprehensive wild turkey management plan. Mississippi Department of Wildlife, Fisheries, and Parks, Jackson, MS USA.

All Harvest and number of hunters, as well as PPH from 2016-2022, provided by Adam Butler, Director of Conservation Development, Mississippi Department of Wildlife, Fisheries, and Parks, Jackson, Mississippi, USA.

Missouri
PPH: 2014-2022
Harvest: 2016-2024

Missouri Department of Conservation. (2025). Turkey reports for past seasons.
<<https://mdc.mo.gov/hunting-trapping/species/turkey/turkey-reports/turkey-reports-past-seasons>> Accessed August 2025.

2017-2024 Missouri Wild Turkey Brood Survey Results

All harvest data and 2014-2017 PPH data provided via N. Oakley, Wild Turkey and Ruffed Grouse Biologist, Missouri Department of Conservation.

North Carolina
PPH: 2007-2022
Harvest: 2009-2024
Number of hunters:
2011-2024

North Carolina Wildlife Resources Commission. (2025). Wild turkey.
<<https://www.ncwildlife.gov/species/wild-turkey>> Accessed August 2025.

2007-2022 Wild Turkey Summer Observation Surveys

North Carolina Wildlife Resources Commission. (2025). Harvest Statistics.
<<https://www.ncwildlife.gov/hunting/harvest-statistics#StateHunterHarvestSurveyEstimates-1441>> Accessed October 2025.

State Turkey Hunter Harvest Survey Estimates 2009-2023

Access to state Turkey Hunter Harvest Survey Estimate 2023-2024 report provided by H. Plumpton, Upland Game Bird Biologist, North Carolina Wildlife Resource Commission, Raleigh, North Carolina, USA.

Ohio
PPH: 2014-2022
Harvest: 2016-2024

Ohio Department of Natural Resources – Division of Wildlife. (2025). Summer wild turkey survey: 1999-2025.
<https://mcusercontent.com/9762d9943f454cab103416c32/_compressed/3af01921-be2f-a4a7-daa2-c4021b9545a2.jpg> Accessed August 2025.

Ohio Department of Natural Resources – Division of Wildlife. (2025). Turkey harvest summary. <<https://ohiodnr.gov/discover-and-learn/safety-conservation/wildlife-management/wildlife-population-studies/turkey-harvest-summary>> Accessed August 2025.

2018-2024 Spring Turkey Season Results

Ohio Department of Natural Resources – Division of Wildlife. (2025). Ohio turkey season spring hunting stats 2025.
<https://mcusercontent.com/9762d9943f454cab103416c32/files/0ca30457-6d40-6b24-5da2-80bbb418e896/Turkey_Spring_Season_2025.pdf> Accessed October 2025.

Pennsylvania
PPH: 2008-2022
Harvest: 2010-2024
Number of hunters:
2011-2024

Pennsylvania Game Commission. (2025). Wild turkey.
<<https://www.pa.gov/agencies/pgc/wildlife/discover-pa-wildlife/turkey#accordion-84a88070c5-item-3cdc87014b>> Accessed August 2025.

2018-2024 Wild Turkey Sighting Survey Reports

Casalena, M.J. (2018). Pennsylvania wild turkey management plan. Pennsylvania Game Commission, Harrisburg, Pennsylvania, USA.

Pennsylvania Game Commission. (2025). Big Game Harvest Data. <<https://www.pa.gov/agencies/pgc/huntingandtrapping/harvest-survey-and-data/harvest-data-and-maps/big-game-harvest-data>> Accessed October 2025.

Pennsylvania Game Commission. (2025). Estimated number of hunters by species. <<https://www.pa.gov/agencies/pgc/huntingandtrapping/harvest-survey-and-data/harvest-data-and-maps/estimated-number-of-hunters-by-species>> Accessed April 2025.

South
Carolina

PPH: 2005-2022
Harvest: 2007-2024
Number of hunters:
2007-2024

South Carolina Department of Natural Resources. (2025). Wildlife - Wild Turkeys. <<https://www.dnr.sc.gov/wildlife/turkey/archive.html>> Accessed August 2025.

2005-2022 Wild Turkey Summer Surveys
2007-2022 Turkey Harvest Reports

South Carolina Department of Natural Resources. (2025). Wildlife - Wild Turkeys. <<https://www.dnr.sc.gov/wildlife/turkey/index.html>> Accessed August 2025.

2023-2024 Turkey Harvest Reports

Tennessee

PPH: 2014-2022
Harvest: 2016-2024

Shields, R. (2023). Annual Wild Turkey Status Report 2022. Technical Report 23-1. Tennessee Wildlife Resources Agency, Nashville, Tennessee, USA.

Harvest data provided by R. Shields, Wild Turkey Program Coordinator, Tennessee Wildlife Resources Agency, Nashville, Tennessee, USA.

Table S2. Publicly available PPH, hunter harvest (* 10⁻⁴), and hunter harvest index data. Hunter harvest and hunter harvest index is from two years after the PPH – therefore, for example, for the year 2012, the PPH reported is from 2012, while the hunter harvest and hunter harvest index reported is from 2014. Data that was provided by state agency personnel is not included and labeled ‘redacted’ (please refer to Table S1 for details).

Year	State	PPH	Spring harvest * 10 ⁻⁴ (two years after PPH)	Hunter harvest index (two years after PPH)
2011	Alabama	2.1	4.060	0.765
2012	Alabama	2.0	4.225	0.703
2013	Alabama	1.4	3.982	0.718
2014	Alabama	1.7	2.989	0.710
2015	Alabama	1.7	1.889	0.442
2016	Alabama	1.7	2.747	0.579
2017	Alabama	1.7	2.565	0.532
2018	Alabama	2.0	3.467	0.578
2019	Alabama	1.8	2.500	0.434
2020	Alabama	1.6	3.574	0.505
2021	Alabama	1.8	4.708	0.685
2022	Alabama	1.7	3.566	0.529
2010	Arkansas	1.4	0.893	
2011	Arkansas	1.2	0.912	
2012	Arkansas	2.8	1.207	
2013	Arkansas	1.8	1.156	
2014	Arkansas	1.5	1.186	
2015	Arkansas	1.2	1.007	
2016	Arkansas	1.1	0.788	
2017	Arkansas	0.9	0.822	
2018	Arkansas	1.0	0.858	
2019	Arkansas	1.1	0.701	Redacted
2020	Arkansas	1.5	0.758	Redacted
2021	Arkansas	1.5	0.919	Redacted
2022	Arkansas	1.8	0.930	Redacted
2023	Arkansas	1.8	1.133	Redacted
2019	Florida	2.0	1.301	0.498
2020	Florida	1.9	1.287	0.509
2021	Florida	2.3	1.138	0.454
2022	Florida	2.0	1.451	0.467
2015	Georgia	1.4	2.570	0.513
2016	Georgia	1.7	1.707	0.380
2017	Georgia	1.1	1.707	0.363
2018	Georgia	1.6	1.705	0.377
2019	Georgia	1.5	1.876	0.344
2020	Georgia	1.4	1.097	0.292

2022	Georgia	1.5	1.192	0.307
2000	Indiana	3.1	1.058	0.279
2001	Indiana	3.3	1.037	0.258
2002	Indiana	3.2	1.077	0.256
2003	Indiana	2.4	1.116	0.225
2004	Indiana	4.4	1.319	0.259
2005	Indiana	2.3	1.116	0.209
2006	Indiana	2.6	1.220	0.222
2007	Indiana	2.6	1.299	0.220
2008	Indiana	2.6	1.374	0.242
2009	Indiana	2.4	1.167	0.208
2010	Indiana	2.1	1.266	0.220
2011	Indiana	1.5	1.137	0.187
2012	Indiana	2.5	1.087	0.184
2013	Indiana	2.0	1.185	0.213
2014	Indiana	2.9	1.208	0.214
2015	Indiana	2.8	1.307	0.222
2016	Indiana	2.3	1.131	0.188
2017	Indiana	2.7	1.201	0.201
2018	Indiana	2.8	1.449	0.195
2019	Indiana	2.2	1.232	
2020	Indiana	2.3	1.253	
2021	Indiana	4.0	1.665	
2022	Indiana	2.8	1.555	
2008	Iowa	1.9	1.089	
2009	Iowa	1.6	0.953	
2010	Iowa	2.0	1.046	
2011	Iowa	1.8	1.057	
2012	Iowa	2.3	1.140	
2013	Iowa	1.7	1.141	
2015	Iowa	1.8	1.178	
2016	Iowa	2.2	1.170	
2017	Iowa	2.1	1.139	
2018	Iowa	2.1	1.469	
2019	Iowa	1.6	1.173	
2020	Iowa	2.0	1.195	
2021	Iowa	2.6	1.484	
2022	Iowa	2.6	1.609	
2023	Iowa	2.4	1.535	
2019	Kentucky	2.4	2.922	
2020	Kentucky	2.4	2.686	
2021	Kentucky	3.2	3.566	
2022	Kentucky	2.3	3.347	
2014	Mississippi	1.9	Redacted	
2015	Mississippi	1.7	Redacted	

2016	Mississippi	Redacted	Redacted	
2017	Mississippi	Redacted	Redacted	
2018	Mississippi	Redacted	Redacted	
2019	Mississippi	Redacted	Redacted	Redacted
2020	Mississippi	Redacted	Redacted	Redacted
2021	Mississippi	Redacted	Redacted	Redacted
2022	Mississippi	Redacted	Redacted	Redacted
2014	Missouri	Redacted	Redacted	
2015	Missouri	Redacted	Redacted	
2016	Missouri	Redacted	Redacted	
2017	Missouri	Redacted	Redacted	
2018	Missouri	0.9	Redacted	
2019	Missouri	0.9	Redacted	
2020	Missouri	1.0	Redacted	
2021	Missouri	1.0	Redacted	
2022	Missouri	1.0	Redacted	
2007	North Carolina	1.9	1.258	
2008	North Carolina	2.2	1.376	
2009	North Carolina	1.8	1.418	0.212
2010	North Carolina	2.0	1.509	0.263
2011	North Carolina	2.2	1.841	0.297
2012	North Carolina	1.6	1.691	0.250
2013	North Carolina	1.6	1.739	0.243
2014	North_Carolina	2.0	1.756	0.256
2015	North Carolina	1.9	1.892	0.247
2016	North Carolina	1.5	1.741	0.251
2017	North Carolina	1.8	1.873	0.263
2018	North Carolina	1.8	2.343	0.322
2019	North Carolina	2.2	2.197	0.291
2020	North Carolina	1.3	2.058	0.271
2021	North Carolina	1.8	2.409	0.322
2022	North Carolina	1.6	Redacted	Redacted
2014	Ohio	2.2	1.781	
2015	Ohio	2.7	2.110	
2016	Ohio	3.8	2.261	
2017	Ohio	2.2	1.909	
2018	Ohio	2.0	1.789	
2019	Ohio	2.3	1.455	
2020	Ohio	2.7	1.187	
2021	Ohio	3.1	1.567	
2022	Ohio	3.0	1.554	
2023	Ohio	2.8	1.601	
2008	Pennsylvania	2.6	3.191	
2009	Pennsylvania	2.2	3.177	0.144
2010	Pennsylvania	1.7	3.562	0.170

2011	Pennsylvania	1.7	3.416	0.165
2012	Pennsylvania	2.1	3.951	0.189
2013	Pennsylvania	2.5	3.993	0.201
2014	Pennsylvania	2.3	3.451	0.178
2015	Pennsylvania	2.5	3.697	0.230
2016	Pennsylvania	2.5	3.908	0.239
2017	Pennsylvania	2.3	3.564	0.213
2018	Pennsylvania	2.4	3.288	0.181
2019	Pennsylvania	2.8	2.678	0.178
2020	Pennsylvania	2.7	3.407	0.216
2021	Pennsylvania	3.1	3.952	0.246
2022	Pennsylvania	3.1	3.927	0.243
2005	South Carolina	1.6	1.929	0.456
2006	South Carolina	1.7	1.730	0.373
2007	South Carolina	1.5	1.623	0.364
2008	South Carolina	2.1	1.692	0.390
2009	South Carolina	1.8	1.709	0.422
2010	South Carolina	2.6	2.155	0.520
2011	South Carolina	2.3	1.921	0.379
2012	South Carolina	1.9	1.625	0.354
2013	South Carolina	1.3	1.524	0.345
2014	South Carolina	1.6	1.678	0.324
2015	South Carolina	1.5	1.917	0.366
2016	South Carolina	1.8	1.794	0.353
2017	South Carolina	1.5	1.737	0.354
2018	South Carolina	1.7	1.406	0.326
2019	South Carolina	1.4	1.407	0.273
2020	South Carolina	1.5	1.349	0.282
2021	South Carolina	2.0	1.307	0.281
2022	South Carolina	1.3	1.243	0.264
2014	Tennessee	2.6	Redacted	
2015	Tennessee	2.6	Redacted	
2016	Tennessee	2.0	Redacted	
2017	Tennessee	2.0	Redacted	
2018	Tennessee	2.6	Redacted	
2019	Tennessee	2.4	Redacted	
2020	Tennessee	1.9	Redacted	
2021	Tennessee	2.8	Redacted	
2022	Tennessee	2.8	Redacted	
